

GENERALIZED CANAVATI TYPE g -FRACTIONAL IYENGAR AND OSTROWSKI TYPE INEQUALITIES

GEORGE A. ANASTASSIOU

ABSTRACT. We present here generalized Canavati type g -fractional Iyengar and Ostrowski type inequalities. Our inequalities are with respect to all L_p norms: $1 \leq p \leq \infty$. We finish with applications.

1. BACKGROUND - I

We are motivated by the following famous Iyengar inequality (1938), [7].

Theorem 1.1. *Let f be a differentiable function on $[a, b]$ and $|f'(x)| \leq M$. Then*

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \frac{1}{2}(b-a)(f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \frac{M(b-a)^2}{4} - \frac{(f(b) - f(a))^2}{4M}. \quad (1)$$

We need the following fractional calculus background:

Let $\alpha > 0$, $m = [\alpha]$, ($[\cdot]$ is the integral part), $\beta = \alpha - m$, $0 < \beta < 1$, $f \in C([a, b])$, $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$, $x \in [a, b]$. The gamma function Γ is given by $\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-t} t^{\alpha-1} dt$. We define the left Riemann-Liouville integral ([1], p. 24)

$$(J_{a+}^{\alpha} f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (2)$$

$a \leq x \leq b$. We define the subspace $C_{a+}^{\alpha}([a, b])$ of $C^m([a, b])$:

$$C_{a+}^{\alpha}([a, b]) = \left\{ f \in C^m([a, b]) : J_{1-\beta}^{a+} f^{(m)} \in C^1([a, b]) \right\}. \quad (3)$$

For $f \in C_{a+}^{\alpha}([a, b])$, we define the left generalized α -fractional derivative of f over $[a, b]$ as

$$D_{a+}^{\alpha} f := \left(J_{1-\beta}^{a+} f^{(m)} \right)', \quad (4)$$

see [1], p. 24. Canavati first in [6] introduced the above over $[0, 1]$.

We have that $D_{a+}^n f = f^{(n)}$; $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Notice that $D_{a+}^{\alpha} f \in C([a, b])$.

Furthermore we need:

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 26A33, 26D10, 26D15.

Key words and phrases. Iyengar inequality; Ostrowski inequality; generalized fractional derivative; Canavati fractional derivative.

Let again $\alpha > 0$, $m = [\alpha]$, $\beta = \alpha - m$, $f \in C([a, b])$, call the right Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator by

$$(J_{b-}^{\alpha} f)(x) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (5)$$

$x \in [a, b]$, see [2]. Define the subspace of functions

$$C_{b-}^{\alpha}([a, b]) = \left\{ f \in C^m([a, b]) : J_{b-}^{1-\beta} f^{(m)} \in C^1([a, b]) \right\}. \quad (6)$$

Define the right generalized α -fractional derivative of f over $[a, b]$ as

$$D_{b-}^{\alpha} f = (-1)^{m-1} \left(J_{b-}^{1-\beta} f^{(m)} \right)', \quad (7)$$

see [2]. We set $D_{b-}^0 f = f$. We have $D_{b-}^n f = (-1)^n f^{(n)}$; $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Notice that $D_{b-}^{\alpha} f \in C([a, b])$.

From [5] we have the following Canavati fractional Iyengar type inequalities:

Theorem 1.2. *Let $\nu \geq 1$, $n = [\nu]$ and $f \in C_{a+}^{\nu}([a, b]) \cap C_{b-}^{\nu}([a, b])$. Then*

i)

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[f^{(k)}(a) (t-a)^{k+1} + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) (b-t)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left[(t-a)^{\nu+1} + (b-t)^{\nu+1} \right], \quad (8)$$

$\forall t \in [a, b]$,

ii) at $t = \frac{a+b}{2}$, the right hand side of (8) is minimized, and we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(b-a)^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \left[f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu+1}}{2^{\nu}}, \quad (9)$$

iii) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu+1}}{2^{\nu}}, \quad (10)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

iv) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{k+1} \left[j^{k+1} f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \quad (11)$$

v) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (11) we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right) [j f(a) + (N-j) f(b)] \right| \leq$$

$$\frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu + 2)} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \quad (12)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

vi) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (12) turns to

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{\infty, ([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu + 2)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu+1}}{2^{\nu}}. \quad (13)$$

We continue with L_1 estimates:

Theorem 1.3. ([5]) Let $\nu \geq 1$, $n = [\nu]$, and $f \in C_{a+}^{\nu}([a, b]) \cap C_{b-}^{\nu}([a, b])$. Then

i)

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[f^{(k)}(a) (t-a)^{k+1} + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) (b-t)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} [(t-a)^{\nu} + (b-t)^{\nu}], \quad (14)$$

$\forall t \in [a, b]$,

ii) when $\nu = 1$, from (14), we have

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - [f(a)(t-a) + f(b)(b-t)] \right| \leq \|f'\|_{L_1([a, b])} (b-a), \quad \forall t \in [a, b], \quad (15)$$

iii) from (15), we obtain ($\nu = 1$ case)

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \|f'\|_{L_1([a, b])} (b-a), \quad (16)$$

iv) at $t = \frac{a+b}{2}$, $\nu > 1$, the right hand side of (14) is minimized, and we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(b-a)^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \left[f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu}}{2^{\nu-1}}, \quad (17)$$

v) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$; $\nu > 1$, from (17), we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a, b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu}}{2^{\nu-1}}, \quad (18)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

vi) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{k+1} \left[j^{k+1} f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+1)} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu} [j^{\nu} + (N-j)^{\nu}], \quad (19)$$

vii) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (19) we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right) [jf(a) + (N-j)f(b)] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+1)} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu} [j^{\nu} + (N-j)^{\nu}], \quad (20)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

viii) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (20) turns to

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \frac{(b-a)}{2} (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_1([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu+1)} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu}}{2^{\nu-1}}, \quad (21)$$

We continue with L_p estimates:

Theorem 1.4. ([5]) Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, $\nu \geq 1$, $n = [\nu]$; $f \in C_{a+}^{\nu}([a, b]) \cap C_{b-}^{\nu}([a, b])$. Then

$$i) \left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[f^{(k)}(a) (t-a)^{k+1} + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) (b-t)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left[(t-a)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} + (b-t)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \right], \quad (22)$$

$\forall t \in [a, b]$,

ii) at $t = \frac{a+b}{2}$, the right hand side of (22) is minimized, and we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(b-a)^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \left[f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}, \quad (23)$$

iii) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\}}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \frac{(b-a)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}, \quad (24)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

iv) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{k+1} \left[j^{k+1} f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} f^{(k)}(b) \right] \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \left[j^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} + (N-j)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \right],}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}}, \quad (25)$$

ν) if $f^{(k)}(a) = f^{(k)}(b) = 0, k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (25) we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right) [jf(a) + (N-j)f(b)] \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\} \left(\frac{b-a}{N} \right)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \left[j^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} + (N-j)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \right],}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}}, \quad (26)$$

for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

vi) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (26) turns to

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dx - \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \frac{\max \left\{ \|D_{a+}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])}, \|D_{b-}^{\nu} f\|_{L_q([a,b])} \right\} (b-a)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}} \cdot 2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}. \quad (27)$$

Next we follow [4].

Let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a strictly increasing function. Let $f \in C^n([a, b]), n \in \mathbb{N}$. Assume that $g \in C^1([a, b])$, and $g^{-1} \in C^n([a, b])$. Call $l := f \circ g^{-1} : [g(a), g(b)] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. It is clear that $l, l', \dots, l^{(n)}$ are continuous functions from $[g(a), g(b)]$ into $f([a, b]) \subseteq \mathbb{R}$.

Let $\nu \geq 1$ such that $[\nu] = n, n \in \mathbb{N}$ as above, where $[\cdot]$ is the integral part of the number.

Clearly when $0 < \nu < 1, [\nu] = 0$. Next we follow [1], pp. 7-9.

I) Let $h \in C([g(a), g(b)])$, we define the left Riemann-Liouville fractional integral as

$$(J_{\nu}^{z_0} h)(z) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{z_0}^z (z-t)^{\nu-1} h(t) dt, \quad (28)$$

for $g(a) \leq z_0 \leq z \leq g(b)$, where Γ is the gamma function; $\Gamma(\nu) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{\nu-1} dt$.

We set $J_0^{z_0} h = h$.

Let $\alpha := \nu - [\nu] (0 < \alpha < 1)$. We define the subspace $C_{g(x_0)}^{\nu}([g(a), g(b)])$ of $C^{[\nu]}([g(a), g(b)])$, where $x_0 \in [a, b]$:

$$C_{g(x_0)}^{\nu}([g(a), g(b)]) := \left\{ h \in C^{[\nu]}([g(a), g(b)]) : J_{1-\alpha}^{g(x_0)} h^{([\nu])} \in C^1([g(x_0), g(b)]) \right\}. \quad (29)$$

So let $h \in C_{g(x_0)}^{\nu}([g(a), g(b)])$; we define the left g -generalized fractional derivative of h of order ν , of Canavati type, over $[g(x_0), g(b)]$ as

$$D_{g(x_0)}^{\nu} h := \left(J_{1-\alpha}^{g(x_0)} h^{([\nu])} \right)'. \quad (30)$$

Clearly, for $h \in C_{g(x_0)}^{\nu}([g(a), g(b)])$, there exists

$$\left(D_{g(x_0)}^{\nu} h \right)(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dz} \int_{g(x_0)}^z (z-t)^{-\alpha} h^{([\nu])}(t) dt, \quad (31)$$

for all $g(x_0) \leq z \leq g(b)$.

In particular, when $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)])$ we have that

$$\left(D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dz} \int_{g(x_0)}^z (z-t)^{-\alpha} (f \circ g^{-1})^{([\nu])} (t) dt, \quad (32)$$

for all $g(x_0) \leq z \leq g(b)$. We have $D_{g(x_0)}^n (f \circ g^{-1}) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(n)}$ and $D_{g(x_0)}^0 (f \circ g^{-1}) = f \circ g^{-1}$.

II) Next we follow [3], pp. 345-348.

Let $h \in C([g(a), g(b)])$, we define the right Riemann-Liouville fractional integral as

$$(J_{z_0-}^\nu h)(z) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_z^{z_0} (t-z)^{\nu-1} h(t) dt, \quad (33)$$

for $g(a) \leq z \leq z_0 \leq g(b)$. We set $J_{z_0-}^0 h = h$.

Let $\alpha := \nu - [\nu]$ ($0 < \alpha < 1$). We define the subspace $C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)])$ of $C^{[\nu]}([g(a), g(b)])$, where $x_0 \in [a, b]$:

$$C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)]) := \left\{ h \in C^{[\nu]}([g(a), g(b)]) : J_{g(x_0)-}^{1-\alpha} h^{([\nu])} \in C^1([g(a), g(x_0)]) \right\}. \quad (34)$$

So let $h \in C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)])$; we define the right g -generalized fractional derivative of h of order ν , of Canavati type, over $[g(a), g(x_0)]$ as

$$D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu h := (-1)^{n-1} \left(J_{g(x_0)-}^{1-\alpha} h^{([\nu])} \right)'. \quad (35)$$

Clearly, for $h \in C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)])$, there exists

$$\left(D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu h \right) (z) = \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dz} \int_z^{g(x_0)} (t-z)^{-\alpha} h^{([\nu])} (t) dt, \quad (36)$$

for all $g(a) \leq z \leq g(x_0) \leq g(b)$.

In particular, when $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu ([g(a), g(b)])$ we have that

$$\left(D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (z) = \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dz} \int_z^{g(x_0)} (t-z)^{-\alpha} (f \circ g^{-1})^{([\nu])} (t) dt, \quad (37)$$

for all $g(a) \leq z \leq g(x_0) \leq g(b)$.

We get that

$$\left(D_{g(x_0)-}^n (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (z) = (-1)^n (f \circ g^{-1})^{(n)} (z) \quad (38)$$

and $\left(D_{g(x_0)-}^0 (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (z) = (f \circ g^{-1})(z)$, all $z \in [g(a), g(x_0)]$.

Let g be strictly increasing and continuous over $[a, b]$, and $f \in C([a, b])$. We have that

$$\int_a^b f(x) dg(x) = \int_a^b (f \circ g^{-1})(g(x)) dg(x) = \int_{g(a)}^{g(b)} (f \circ g^{-1})(z) dz. \quad (39)$$

Here it is $f \circ g^{-1} \in C([g(a), g(b)])$.

2. MAIN RESULTS - I

Next we present generalized g -fractional Iyengar type inequalities:

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\nu \geq 1$ such that $[\nu] = n \in \mathbb{N}$, and $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a strictly increasing function. Assume that $f \in C^n([a, b])$, $g \in C^1([a, b])$, $g^{-1} \in C^n([g(a), g(b)])$.*

Assume further that $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(a)}^\nu([g(a), g(b)]) \cap C_{g(b)-}^\nu([g(a), g(b)])$. Set

$$M_1(f, g) := \max \left\{ \left\| D_{g(a)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(b)]}, \left\| D_{g(b)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(b)]} \right\}. \quad (40)$$

Then

i)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a))(z-g(a))^{k+1} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b))(g(b)-z)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \\ & \quad \frac{M_1(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left[(z-g(a))^{\nu+1} + (g(b)-z)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

$\forall z \in [g(a), g(b)]$,

ii) at $z = \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2}$, the right hand side of (41) is minimized, and we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \leq \\ & \quad \frac{M_1(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{\nu+1}}{2^\nu}, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

iii) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) \right| \leq \frac{M_1(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{\nu+1}}{2^\nu}, \quad (43)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

iv) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{k+1} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left[j^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{M_1(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

v) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (44) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right) [jf(a) + (N-j)f(b)] \right| \leq \\ & \quad \frac{M_1(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

vi) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (45) turns to

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \frac{M_1(f, g) (g(b) - g(a))^{\nu+1}}{\Gamma(\nu + 2) 2^\nu}. \quad (46)$$

Proof. Apply Theorem 1.2 for $f \circ g^{-1}$ over $[g(a), g(b)]$ and take into account (39). $\square$

Next come L_1 estimates:

Theorem 2.2. *All as in Theorem 2.1. Set*

$$M_2(f, g) := \max \left\{ \left\| D_{g(a)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_1[g(a), g(b)]}, \left\| D_{g(b)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_1[g(a), g(b)]} \right\}. \quad (47)$$

Then

i)

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) (z - g(a))^{k+1} + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) (g(b) - z)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \frac{M_2(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} [(z - g(a))^\nu + (g(b) - z)^\nu], \quad (48)$$

$\forall z \in [g(a), g(b)]$,

ii) when $\nu = 1$, from (48), we have

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - [f(a)(z - g(a)) + f(b)(g(b) - z)] \right| \leq \left\| (f \circ g^{-1})' \right\|_{L_1([g(a), g(b)])} (g(b) - g(a)), \quad (49)$$

$\forall z \in [g(a), g(b)]$,

iii) from (49) we obtain ($\nu = 1$ case)

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \left\| (f \circ g^{-1})' \right\|_{L_1([g(a), g(b)])} (g(b) - g(a)), \quad (50)$$

iv) at $z = \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2}$, $\nu > 1$, the right hand side of (48) is minimized, and we get:

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(g(b) - g(a))^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \leq \frac{M_2(f, g) (g(b) - g(a))^\nu}{\Gamma(\nu + 1) 2^{\nu-1}}, \quad (51)$$

v) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$; $\nu > 1$, from (51), we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) \right| \leq \frac{M_2(f, g) (g(b) - g(a))^\nu}{\Gamma(\nu + 1) 2^{\nu-1}}, \quad (52)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

vi) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{N} \right)^{k+1} \right. \\ & \left. \left[j^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{M_2(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{N} \right)^\nu [j^\nu + (N-j)^\nu], \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

vii) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (53) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{N} \right) [jf(a) + (N-j)f(b)] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_2(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{N} \right)^\nu [j^\nu + (N-j)^\nu], \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

viii) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (54) turns to

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b) - g(a)}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_2(f, g) (g(b) - g(a))^\nu}{\Gamma(\nu + 1) 2^{\nu-1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

Proof. Application of Theorem 1.3 for $f \circ g^{-1}$ over $[g(a), g(b)]$ and take into account (39). $\square$

We continue with L_p estimates:

Theorem 2.3. All as in Theorem 2.1. Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Set

$$M_3(f, g) := \max \left\{ \left\| D_{g(a)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q[g(a), g(b)]}, \left\| D_{g(b)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q[g(a), g(b)]} \right\}. \quad (56)$$

Then

i)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) (z - g(a))^{k+1} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) (g(b) - z)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p} \right) (p(\nu - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left[(z - g(a))^{\nu + \frac{1}{p}} + (g(b) - z)^{\nu + \frac{1}{p}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

$\forall z \in [g(a), g(b)]$,

ii) at $z = \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2}$, the right hand side of (57) is minimized, and we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \right. \\ & \left. \left[(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

iii) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) \right| \leq \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}, \quad (59)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

iv) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{k+1} \right. \\ & \left. \left[j^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) \right] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \left[j^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} + (N-j)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

v) if $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(a)) = (f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(b)) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (60) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right) [jf(a) + (N-j)f(b)] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{N} \right)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \left[j^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} + (N-j)^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

vi) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (61) turns to

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - \left(\frac{g(b)-g(a)}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_3(f, g)}{\Gamma(\nu) \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right) (p(\nu-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \frac{(g(b)-g(a))^{\nu+\frac{1}{p}}}{2^{\nu-\frac{1}{q}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

Proof. Application of Theorem 1.4 to $f \circ g^{-1}$ over $[g(a), g(b)]$ and using (39). $\square$

3. BACKGROUND - II

In 1938, A. Ostrowski [8] proved the following important inequality.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous on $[a, b]$ and differentiable on (a, b) whose derivative $f' : (a, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is bounded on (a, b) , i.e., $\|f'\|_\infty := \sup_{t \in (a, b)} |f'(t)| < +\infty$.*

Then

$$\left| \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt - f(x) \right| \leq \left[\frac{1}{4} + \frac{\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^2}{(b-a)^2} \right] \cdot (b-a) \|f'\|_\infty, \quad (63)$$

for any $x \in [a, b]$. The constant $\frac{1}{4}$ is the best possible.

Since then there has been a lot of activity around these inequalities with important applications to numerical analysis and probability.

We mention and need the following left generalized g -fractional, of Canavati type, Taylor's formula:

Theorem 3.2. ([4]) Let $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)}^\nu([g(a), g(b)])$, where $x_0 \in [a, b]$ is fixed, $\nu \geq 1$. Then

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = \sum_{k=1}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(x_0))}{k!} (g(x) - g(x_0))^k + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x_0)}^{g(x)} (g(x) - t)^{\nu-1} \left(D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right)(t) dt, \quad \text{all } x \in [a, b] : x \geq x_0. \quad (64)$$

We also mention and need the following right generalized g -fractional, of Canavati type, Taylor's formula:

Theorem 3.3. ([4]) Let $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu([g(a), g(b)])$, where $x_0 \in [a, b]$ is fixed, $\nu \geq 1$. Then

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = \sum_{k=1}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(x_0))}{k!} (g(x) - g(x_0))^k + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x)}^{g(x_0)} (t - g(x))^{\nu-1} \left(D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right)(t) dt, \quad \text{all } a \leq x \leq x_0. \quad (65)$$

4. MAIN RESULTS - II

Next we present generalized g -fractional Ostrowski type inequalities:

Theorem 4.1. Let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a strictly increasing function, $\nu \geq 1$, $[\nu] = n \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in C^n([a, b])$. Assume that $g \in C^1([a, b])$, and $g^{-1} \in C^n([g(a), g(b)])$. For $x_0 \in [a, b]$, assume that $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)}^\nu([g(a), g(b)])$ and $f \circ g^{-1} \in C_{g(x_0)-}^\nu([g(a), g(b)])$.

Furthermore assume that $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(x_0)) = 0$, all $k = 1, \dots, n-1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - f(x_0) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \left\{ \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]} (g(x_0) - g(a))^{\nu+1} + \right. \\ & \left. \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} (g(b) - g(x_0))^{\nu+1} \right\} \leq \\ & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \max \left\{ \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]}, \right. \\ & \left. \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} \right\} (g(b) - g(a))^\nu. \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.2, when $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(x_0)) = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, we get

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x_0)}^{g(x)} (g(x) - t)^{\nu-1} \left(D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (t) dt, \quad (67)$$

$\forall x \in [x_0, b]$.

By Theorem 3.3, when $(f \circ g^{-1})^{(k)}(g(x_0)) = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, we get

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x)}^{g(x_0)} (t - g(x))^{\nu-1} \left(D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (t) dt, \quad (68)$$

$\forall x \in [a, x_0]$.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x) - f(x_0)| &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x_0)}^{g(x)} (g(x) - t)^{\nu-1} \left| \left(D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (t) \right| dt \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \left(\int_{g(x_0)}^{g(x)} (g(x) - t)^{\nu-1} dt \right) \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \frac{(g(x) - g(x_0))^\nu}{\nu} \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} \\ &= \frac{(g(x) - g(x_0))^\nu}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]}, \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

$\forall x \in [x_0, b]$.

That is

$$|f(x) - f(x_0)| \leq \frac{\left\| D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} (g(x) - g(x_0))^\nu, \quad (70)$$

$\forall x \in [x_0, b]$.

Similarly, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x) - f(x_0)| &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_{g(x)}^{g(x_0)} (t - g(x))^{\nu-1} \left| \left(D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right) (t) \right| dt \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \left(\int_{g(x)}^{g(x_0)} (t - g(x))^{\nu-1} dt \right) \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]} \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} (g(x_0) - g(x))^\nu \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]}, \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

$\forall x \in [a, x_0]$.

That is

$$|f(x) - f(x_0)| \leq \frac{\left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} (g(x_0) - g(x))^\nu, \quad (72)$$

$\forall x \in [a, x_0]$.

We observe that

$$\left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b f(x) g'(x) dx - f(x_0) \right| =$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b f(x) g'(x) dx - f(x_0) (g(b) - g(a)) \right| = \\ & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \left[\int_a^b f(x) g'(x) dx - \int_a^b f(x_0) g'(x) dx \right] \right| = \\ & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \left[\int_a^b (f(x) - f(x_0)) g'(x) dx \right] \right| \leq \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b |f(x) - f(x_0)| g'(x) dx = \\ & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \left\{ \int_a^{x_0} |f(x) - f(x_0)| g'(x) dx + \int_{x_0}^b |f(x) - f(x_0)| g'(x) dx \right\} \\ & \stackrel{\text{(by (70), (72))}}{\leq} \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \left\{ \frac{\|D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \int_a^{x_0} (g(x_0) - g(x))^\nu g'(x) dx + \right. \\ & \quad \left. \frac{\|D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]}}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \int_{x_0}^b (g(x) - g(x_0))^\nu g'(x) dx \right\} = \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a)) \Gamma(\nu + 2)} \left\{ \|D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]} (g(x_0) - g(a))^{\nu+1} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \|D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} (g(b) - g(x_0))^{\nu+1} \right\} \leq \\ & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu + 2)} \max \left\{ \|D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(a), g(x_0)]}, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \|D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{\infty, [g(x_0), g(b)]} \right\} (g(b) - g(a))^\nu. \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

□

We continue with an L_1 -estimate:

Theorem 4.2. *All as in Theorem 4.1. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - f(x_0) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a)) \Gamma(\nu + 1)} \left\{ \|D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{L_1([g(a), g(x_0)])} (g(x_0) - g(a))^\nu \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \|D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{L_1[g(x_0), g(b)]} (g(b) - g(x_0))^\nu \right\} \leq \\ & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu + 1)} \max \left\{ \|D_{g(x_0)-}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{L_1([g(a), g(x_0)])}, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \|D_{g(x_0)}^\nu (f \circ g^{-1})\|_{L_1([g(x_0), g(b)])} \right\} (g(b) - g(a))^{\nu-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

Proof. Similar to the proof of Theorem 4.1. $\square$

We continue with an L_p -estimate:

Theorem 4.3. *All as in Theorem 4.1, and let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a))} \int_a^b f(x) dg(x) - f(x_0) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{1}{(g(b) - g(a)) \Gamma(\nu) (p(\nu - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \\ & \left\{ (g(x_0) - g(a))^{\nu + \frac{1}{p}} \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^{\nu} (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q([g(a), g(x_0)])} \right. \\ & \left. + (g(b) - g(x_0))^{\nu + \frac{1}{p}} \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^{\nu} (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q([g(x_0), g(b)])} \right\} \leq \\ & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu) (p(\nu - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\nu + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \max \left\{ \left\| D_{g(x_0)-}^{\nu} (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q([g(a), g(x_0)])}, \right. \\ & \left. \left\| D_{g(x_0)}^{\nu} (f \circ g^{-1}) \right\|_{L_q([g(x_0), g(b)])} \right\} (g(b) - g(a))^{\nu - \frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

Proof. Similar to the proof of Theorem 4.1. $\square$

Applications follow:

Proposition 4.4. *Let $\nu \geq 1$ such that $[\nu] = n \in \mathbb{N}$, and $f \in C^n([a, b])$, where $[a, b] \subset (0, +\infty)$. Assume that $f \circ \ln x \in C_{e^a}^{\nu}([e^a, e^b]) \cap C_{e^b-}^{\nu}([e^a, e^b])$. Set*

$$M_1(f, e^x) := \max \left\{ \left\| D_{e^a}^{\nu} (f \circ \ln x) \right\|_{\infty, [e^a, e^b]}, \left\| D_{e^b-}^{\nu} (f \circ \ln x) \right\|_{\infty, [e^a, e^b]} \right\}. \quad (78)$$

Then

i)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left[(f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^a) (z - e^a)^{k+1} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + (-1)^k (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^b) (e^b - z)^{k+1} \right] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu + 2)} \left[(z - e^a)^{\nu+1} + (e^b - z)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

$\forall z \in [e^a, e^b]$,

ii) at $z = \frac{e^a + e^b}{2}$, the right hand side of (79) is minimized, and we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \frac{(e^b - e^a)^{k+1}}{2^{k+1}} \right. \\ & \left. \left[(f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^a) + (-1)^k (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^b) \right] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu + 2)} \frac{(e^b - e^a)^{\nu+1}}{2^{\nu}}, \end{aligned} \quad (80)$$

iii) if $(f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^a) = (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^b) = 0$, for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, we obtain

$$\left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx \right| \leq \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(e^b - e^a)^{\nu+1}}{2^\nu}, \quad (81)$$

which is a sharp inequality,

iv) more generally, for $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \in \mathbb{N}$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{e^b - e^a}{N} \right)^{k+1} \right. \\ & \left. \left[j^{k+1} (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^a) + (-1)^k (N-j)^{k+1} (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left(\frac{e^b - e^a}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (82)$$

v) if $(f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^a) = (f \circ \ln x)^{(k)}(e^b) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, from (82) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx - \left(\frac{e^b - e^a}{N} \right) [j f(a) + (N-j) f(b)] \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \left(\frac{e^b - e^a}{N} \right)^{\nu+1} \left[j^{\nu+1} + (N-j)^{\nu+1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

$j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$,

vi) when $N = 2$ and $j = 1$, (83) turns to

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b f(x) e^x dx - \left(\frac{e^b - e^a}{2} \right) (f(a) + f(b)) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{M_1(f, e^x)}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \frac{(e^b - e^a)^{\nu+1}}{2^\nu}. \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

Proof. By application of Theorem 2.1 for $g(x) = e^x$. $\square$

We finish with

Proposition 4.5. Let $\nu \geq 1$, $[\nu] = n \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in C^n([a, b])$, $[a, b] \subset (0, +\infty)$. For $x_0 \in [a, b]$, assume that $f \circ e^x \in C_{\ln x_0}^\nu([\ln a, \ln b])$, and $f \circ e^x \in C_{\ln x_0}^\nu([\ln a, \ln b])$.

Furthermore assume that $(f \circ e^x)^{(k)}(\ln x_0) = 0$, all $k = 1, \dots, n-1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\ln \frac{b}{a})} \int_a^b \frac{f(x)}{x} dx - f(x_0) \right| \leq \\ & \frac{1}{(\ln \frac{b}{a}) \Gamma(\nu+2)} \left\{ \|D_{\ln x_0}^\nu (f \circ e^x)\|_{\infty, [\ln a, \ln x_0]} \left(\ln \frac{x_0}{a} \right)^{\nu+1} + \right. \\ & \left. \|D_{\ln x_0}^\nu (f \circ e^x)\|_{\infty, [\ln x_0, \ln b]} \left(\ln \frac{b}{x_0} \right)^{\nu+1} \right\} \leq \\ & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu+2)} \max \left\{ \|D_{\ln x_0}^\nu (f \circ e^x)\|_{\infty, [\ln a, \ln x_0]}, \right. \\ & \left. \|D_{\ln x_0}^\nu (f \circ e^x)\|_{\infty, [\ln x_0, \ln b]} \right\} \left(\ln \frac{b}{a} \right)^\nu. \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

Proof. By Theorem 4.1, for $g(x) = \ln x$. $\square$

REFERENCES

- [1] G.A. Anastassiou. Fractional Differentiation Inequalities, Research Monograph, Springer, New York, 2009.
- [2] G.A. Anastassiou. On Right Fractional Calculus, Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, 42 (2009), 365-376.
- [3] G.A. Anastassiou. Intelligent Mathematics: Computational Analysis, Springer, Heidelberg, 2011.
- [4] G.A. Anastassiou. Generalized Canavati type Fractional Taylor's formulae, J. Computational Analysis and Applications, 21 (7)(2016), 1205-1212.
- [5] G.A. Anastassiou. Canavati fractional Iyengar type Inequalities, Analele Universitatii Oradea, Fasc. Matematica, Tom XXVI (2019) (1), 141-151.
- [6] J.A. Canavati. The Riemann-Liouville Integral, Nieuw Archief Voor Wiskunde, 5 (1) (1987), 53-75.
- [7] K.S.K. Iyengar. Note on a inequality, Math. Student, 6 (1938), 75-76.
- [8] A. Ostrowski. Über die Absolutabweichung einer differtentiebaren Funktion von ihrem Integralmittelwert, Comment. Math. Helv. 10 (1938), 226-227.

GEORGE A. ANASTASSIOU

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF MEMPHIS, MEMPHIS, TN 38152, U.S.A.

Email address: ganastss@memphis.edu